

ANALYSIS OF ACOUSTIC EMISSION SIGNALS PRODUCED BY DIFFERENT CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED PLASTIC LAMINATES

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SUMMARY

Acoustic emission events were generated on composite laminates different in lay up and thickness. The aim was the prediction of the extensional velocity through the elastic moduli of material, calculated by lamination theory. It can allow a good location analysis.

Keywords: acoustic emission, waveform, extensional velocity, location, composites.

ABSTRACT

Standard pencil lead break tests were carried out on unidirectional and symmetric laminates at the most important aim to investigate about the acoustic emission behaviour of the composite materials. Parameters like stacking sequence, thickness and fibre orientation were varied to verify their influence on the acoustic waveform generated by the standard pencil lead break. The extensional mode of propagation was analysed and the related velocity, C_e , was, first, measured from the difference in arrival time of the signal between two successive sensors located on the surface of the unidirectional panels at fixed distances. The data collected were used to find the four elastic constants characterizing the in-plane behaviour of the basic lamina. From them, the prediction of C_e for two symmetric laminates, namely $[0, 90]_{3s}$ and $[0_3, 90_3]_s$, was attempted by lamination theory. To validate the theoretical predictions, additional experimental tests on different architectures were performed and the experimental values were compared with the theory. A quite general good agreement was found.

INTRODUCTION

Acoustic emission technique is the non destructive evaluation today commonly used in very different fields, from industry to health. Its advantage consists in the possibility to investigate about the material behaviour under loading in real time, without any contact, and to know the exact location of the eventual failure without damaging the structure. The AE systems allow to analyse a large number of information about the phenomenon since the very big number of potential parameters offered. Since the high sensitivity of the technique, the latter aspect represents an advantage and a disadvantage at the same time. Each parameter, in fact, can be useful for the comprehension of the damage

phenomenon but it can be influenced by a large number of factors [1] not simple to distinguish each other. Of course, this aspect sensibly complicates the analysis.

All the discussed problems are amplified when the acoustic emission technique is used on composite materials instead of classic homogeneous ones. In fact, the signal is influenced by the fibre presence too and the correlation of the different failure modes to the recorded acoustic signals is, so, very difficult. This is the main reason why the acoustic emission technique is often used to detect just the onset of damage in correspondence of the time of the first emission, or the severity of the damage as the number of the emissions in a fixed period [2-4].

On the other hand, since the growing interest in composite materials in fields like automotive and aeronautical, it is very important a deeper understanding about the behaviour of composite laminates under critical dynamical loads. Another very important aspect is represented by the necessity in the above mentioned fields to investigate about the phenomenon without damaging the structure [5, 6]. Of course, the increasing in the use of composites lead to an increase on the complexity of shapes and, as a consequence, of the damages. Different failures, such as fibre and matrix cracks, debonding and delamination, is possible to observe in composite laminates under mechanical loads and a big number of studies [7-11] were carried out at the aim to verify the influence of parameters like fibre orientations, panel thickness and lay up, on their acoustic emission response under mechanical loads. Efforts were done in order to characterise the damage, correlating the different kind of failure modes described above, to the acoustic emission parameters, in terms of hits, amplitude and energy in particular [12, 13].

The main scope of the present research was, on the contrary, to characterise the composites and their acoustic response, independently of the specific load applied and the damage occurred. The acoustic emission behaviour of square, 300 mm in side, unidirectional CFRP laminates different in thickness was characterized through the measurement of extensional velocity, C_e . The velocity was measured from the difference in arrival time of the signal, generated by the standard pencil lead break, between two successive sensors located on the surface of the panel at fixed distances. From the experimental results, C_e was observed substantially independent of t , whereas, as expected, it was strongly influenced by the fibre orientation. The data collected were used to find the four elastic constants characterizing the in-plane behaviour of the basic lamina. From them, the prediction of C_e for two symmetric laminates, namely $[0, 90]_{3s}$ and $[0_3, 90_3]_s$, was attempted by lamination theory. To validate the theory predictions, additional experimental tests were performed, and the experimental values were compared with the ones obtained by the theory. A quite general good agreement was found.

THEORY

The material under loading modifies its microscopic structure since the atomic displacement. When a damage occurs, the elastic energy is rapidly released. This is the acoustic event [14] that produce the elastic wave propagation in all the directions. Acoustic sensors can be positioned on the structure at the aim to capture the signals to send to the system that allows to visualize and analyse it. The AE testing allow the identification, the location of the source of the event and the interpretation of the recorded signal. The problem is that each kind of damage is related to a different

acoustic wave form and propagation [1]. The waveform consists of many frequencies travelling at different velocities and interference due to reflections, disturbances producing additional noises. So, since the acoustic emission bursts can be originated from disturbances too, such as peaks of the background noise, sometimes the apparently same test conditions could produce different acoustic signals. First of all, setting a right threshold became fundamental, paying attention to not miss important bursts. Then, for what discussed, and for the fact that the different velocities of the different frequencies can introduce errors in the determination of the location [1], the wave form analysis represents a crucial point that need deep studies.

It is mainly possible to distinguish the waveform into low and high frequencies: the first ones are contained into the so called flexural mode wave that since depends on the circular frequency [15], it results dispersive and so very difficult to analyse; on the other hand, the extensional waveform is characterized by higher frequency, no dispersion nor superposition and its direction is longitudinal respect to the sample [1, 8]. For the above mentioned characteristics and for the fact that the extensional mode travels faster and so reach the sensors first, its velocity is usually used for location analysis. The latter can, so, be determined by dividing the preliminarily fixed distance between two successive sensors (x), to the difference in arrival time (Δt_x) of the signal between the closest and the most far sensor, recorded by the system, respectively:

$$C_e = \frac{x}{\Delta t_x} \quad (1)$$

In figure 1 an example of waveform in which it is possible to distinguish the two different modes of propagation was reported.

Figure 1: Generic waveform: extensional and flexural components.

The problem is that each source of an event can have different plate waveforms and not always is possible to distinguish the fundamental two different modes of the waveform propagation and so to calculate the related velocities. Moreover, it is necessary to put in evidence that it is not always clear the difference between the two different modes even if the test conditions are the same. It is probably also due to the existence of the multiple modes of wave propagation related to different and dispersive velocities or the presence

of internal defects of the materials. Disagreement between data obtained in the same conditions were found in literature too [12].

In this field, the theory can be a useful tool, always after a large experimental validation. Following the plate wave theory or Lamb wave theory already reported in many papers [1, 15, 16], the extensional velocity is a function of elastic modulus of the material through the following equation:

$$c_e = \left[\frac{E}{\rho(1-\nu^2)} \right]^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the density and ν the Poisson's ratio. A change in modulus that can occur when a damage happens in the material reflects a change in velocity of sound propagation. The flexural velocity too is a function of the elastic modulus:

$$c_f = \left[\frac{Eh^2}{12\rho(1-\nu^2)} \right]^{1/4} \omega^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

where h is the plate thickness and ω is the circular frequency or the stress frequency. The flexural velocity is so influenced by the plate thickness and by the frequency as above anticipated.

The dependence of both the velocities on the elastic modulus become critical for composite materials where the modulus is a function of the fibre orientation. As a consequence, the velocity too is a function of the disposition of the reinforcement and so of the stacking sequence. This aspect makes very complicated the location analysis in these kind of materials. If the thickness is small respect to the other dimensions, the plate wave theory can again be a useful tool to help the analysis about fracture behaviour and mechanical properties, since each AE signal corresponds to a Lamb wave [16, 17]. It is possible to use the equivalent expression for anisotropic laminates:

$$c_e = \sqrt{\frac{E_x}{\rho(1-\nu_{xy}\nu_{yx})}} \quad (4)$$

where the indexes x , y designate the propagation direction and its perpendicular, respectively. Of course, it is very important to know how the parameters like fibre content and orientation, stacking sequence and panel thickness can influence the modulus and propagation speed and so the waveform. The classical triangulation technique, in fact, cannot be used on anisotropic material since the necessary independence of the wave speed on the direction of propagation [18]. The exact time of the source of an event cannot be measured, so the location of the source of an event can be only made on the analysis of the difference in arrival time, Δt , of the ultrasonic signals between two positioned sensors. The distance difference between the source and the two sensors is calculated by $\Delta t * c$ where c is the signal velocity (fig. 2).

Figure 2: Scheme of the location based on differences in arrival time

EXPERIMENTS

Composite square panels, 300 mm in side, were fabricated by handily overlapping dry unidirectional carbon fibre in a thermosetting matrix, SX10 ($\rho = 1.57 \text{ g/cm}^3$). The obtained laminates were cured by a stamp forming process between aluminium flat moulds on a hydraulic press at room temperature for 24 hours. The applied pressure was about $7.6 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ N/mm}^2$. The panel thickness varied from 0.4 to 4.8 mm following the stacking sequences: $[0]_n$ $n = 1, 4$ and 8 , $[0, 90]_{3s}$, $[0_3, 90_3]_s$.

A mechanical pencil (Fig. 3) with a 0.3 mm (or 0.5 mm) diameter lead was used for the experimental tests: the lead was broken against the CFRP laminates [19] and the produced wave form during each test was recorded by two sensors and successively analysed. 150 kHz resonance ultrasonic emission sensors, type VS150-M, were opportunely located on the laminates along a line differently oriented at the aim to verify the influence of the fibre orientation, at a fixed distance of 200 mm between each other.

Figure 3: Experimental set up.

The signals were amplified at 34 db by AEP3 preamplifiers and recorded by an AMSY4 digital acoustic emission monitoring system (all the AE system is from Vallen-System GmbH). For the acquisition, a 90 KHz lower cut filter, an acquisition rate of 5'000 MHz, a threshold value of 30 db, suggested for composite materials, a pre trigger time of $40 \mu\text{s}$, an acquisition time of maximum 100 ms for each acoustic events and a rearm time of 3.2 ms were adopted. It means that the signal has to go over 30 db for $40 \mu\text{s}$ to

be acquired for 100 ms, then the system stops the acquisition for the following 3.2 ms. After that, it goes in stand by waiting for a new signal overcoming the threshold. A software named Laminator based on the lamination theory was used for the theory predictions. It needs the material properties and the lay up as input and gives the elastic modulus of the laminate and the stiffness matrix as output. More than five tests per each conditions were carried out at the aim to verify the repeatability of the signal.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Linear location was first applied: the two acoustic sensors were positioned on unidirectional laminates as above explained and shown in fig. 3 and the pencil leads were broken against the panel externally to the sensors at fixed distances from them of about 10 mm (figure 3). No significant variations were observed with increasing the distance from the source meaning the non-dispersive nature of the analyzed waves in the range of the adopted distances and the rightness of the method adopted to measure the velocity.

In the first phase of the work, it was possible to distinguish the flexural velocities from the extensional ones on unidirectionals and the latter were measured by equation (1). The results were plotted in figure 4 as a function of fibre orientation for the three unidirectional laminates studied.

Figure 4: Extensional velocity vs fibre orientation for different thickness. Unidirectional laminates.

The plotted points represent the mean values of more than five data. It is immediate to note that the experimental data are negligible affected by the panel thickness whereas the fibre orientation strongly influences the velocity. Of course, the sound speed decreases at the increasing of the fibre angle respect to the sensor linear position. Knowing the material characteristics, laminator software based on classic lamination theory, allowed to predict the elastic moduli and so, the extensional velocity through

equation (2). The experimental data about only four values of fibre orientations (0° , 30° , 45° and 90°) were used for the prediction of the four constants by classical lamination theory (table 1). A good agreement with what obtained by mechanical tests was found. In figure 5, the mean values of the data showed in figure 4 were compared to the theory predictions.

Figure 5: Comparison between experimental and theory.

The continuous line is the graphical expression of equation 2. A reasonable agreement was found.

Of course, what asserted is completely true just for unidirectional laminates. For different stacking sequences, it could be the first lamina, the sequence of the different orientations or the thickness of the layers differently oriented [11] to be the more or less influent for the wave propagation. The latter assertion could be without any meaning from a theory point of view as it will be hereafter underlined.

Table 1: Material characteristics

E_1 (GPa)*	E_2 (GPa)*	G_{12} (GPa)	ν_{12}
64	6	3.5	0.26

*ASTM-D3039, Tensile Properties of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials, PA 19428-2959, United States.

The experimental results in terms of material constants about unidirectional laminates were used for theory prediction on the symmetric laminates. In figure 6 a comparison with additional experimental lead break tests data obtained to support the prediction on $[0/90]_{3s}$ and $[0_3/90_3]_s$, was reported. To draw the curve, the constants in table 1 were used. The material density assumed was $\rho=1.57 \text{ g/cm}^3$. Also in this case a sensible agreement was found denoting the possibility to predict the extensional behaviour of laminates different in stacking sequence from what obtained by experimental tests on unidirectional ones. It will be very important in the case of necessity to localise the source of an event such as a certain damage.

The aim of the experimental tests carried out on symmetric laminates was twofold: first of all to validate the prediction about velocity and then to verify the influence of the stacking sequence. About the first aim, the prediction based on secure data could be very useful also because not always it is possible to simply distinguish the extensional velocity from the flexural one. They are in fact influenced by a lot of factors as explained in the theory section. In figure 7, two waveforms along 0° recorded by the more far sensor about the two different laminates are reported. As it is possible to observe, only in fig. 7b) the extensional mode is clearly visible. A superposition of the flexural mode seems to happen in figure 7a).

Figure 6: Prediction of extensional velocity: symmetric laminates

Figure 7: Comparison between two different waveforms recorded by the 200 mm far sensor: a) $[0_3/90_3]_s$, b) $[0/90]_{3s}$; $\theta = 0^\circ$.

About information on the stacking sequence, by the analysis of the results a different behaviour of the $[0_3/90_3]_s$ laminate respect to the $[0/90]_{3s}$ was observed and the

difference is more pronounced the closer is the 90° orientation. It is not possible to explain the difference from theory since the two laminates has the same in plane modulus. A possible explanation could be due to the effect of the first laminae along the thickness on the waveform propagation and so on the velocity. This is in agreement with the fact that, as it is possible to observe in figure 6, the velocity of the $[0_3/90_3]_s$ laminate in correspondence of the 90° is lower than what expected. It is, at this point, important to remember that the prediction was very good in the case of unidirectional laminates. Of course, deep studies on additional tests on laminates characterised by different stacking sequences will be necessary.

CONCLUSIONS

Pencil lead break tests carried out on CFRP laminates different in lay-up, thickness and fibre orientation, at the aim to characterise the acoustic behaviour of this kind of material, lead to the following results:

- in the range of the analyzed parameters, the effect of the thickness on the extensional velocity was found to be negligible whereas the latter is strongly influenced by the fibre orientation. As expected, the extensional velocity decreases at the increasing of fibre orientation;
- two different methods, experiments and theory, were adopted to obtain the extensional velocity and a quite good agreement between them was found, irrespective of fibre orientation and laminate;
- an analytical tool was assessed for the prediction of the extensional velocity as a function of the fibre orientation; the validity is very good for unidirectional laminates. The results is very important at the light of future damage location;
- a difference in AE behaviour was found between $[0/90]_{3s}$ and $[0_3/90_3]_s$ laminates: the influence of the stacking sequence on the sound velocity was found to be almost negligible up to 15° of fibre orientation and more significant the closer is 90° of fibre angle.

As already said, it is not possible to found the reason of the difference in the theory. Probably, the waveform is influenced by the position of the first laminae. Future research will be devoted to the study of the acoustic behaviour of laminate with different lay ups. Moreover, to confirm what asserted it should be sure the separation between the extensional mode and the flexural one.

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